

The EU long-term budget 2028-34 and Erasmus+

A call for matching
the funding with policy
priorities

Erasmus+ is a flagship European Programme that is an investment in the future of Europe, in competitiveness, in skills, in mutual understanding through cultural exchange, and in shared EU values including democratic participation. For these highlighted reasons, the Draghi report (2024)¹ suggests a fivefold increase in the Erasmus+ budget in the next Multi-Annual Financial Framework (MFF) of the European Union to be able to deliver on making Erasmus available for all. Yet, the current Erasmus+ 2028-34² proposal from the European Commission raises great concerns over these ambitions and falls short of the recommended budgetary increase.

In short

The proposed budget for Erasmus+ 2028-34 will likely not result in an increase for higher education:

- The MFF proposal from the European Commission clearly shows stagnating annual budgets for Erasmus+ compared to the current programming period. At the same time, sizeable new actions are being added to the programme.
- To meet the EU mobility target in higher education of 23% by 2030 as endorsed by the EU, the current allocation to Erasmus+ mobilities should increase by at least 55% based on the 2025 annual budget. This would require an additional budget of at least 5,1 billion EUR, not even considering the funding needs of ambitious initiatives such as the European University Alliances or the new Talent Scholarships.

In the forthcoming negotiation phase between Members of the European Parliament and Member States, we call on Universities and their stakeholder organisations to voice these concerns to their decision-makers. A more detailed explanation follows below.

Is the next MFF budget for Erasmus+ really an increase?

With a budget of 26.2 billion euros for the programming period 2021-2027, the European Commission presented a long-term budget proposal for 2028-34, allocating 40.8 billion³ euros to Erasmus+. While this could be perceived as a 50% increase, this figure does not account for inflation, which in recent years has been impacting the higher education sector just as much as other sectors. If one takes inflation into account, the budget increase would be closer to a 30% rise⁴.

Yet, this is not the full picture. With the Erasmus+ programme and the European Solidarity Corps, budgeted at 1 billion euros for 2021-2027, merging, we are witnessing a further squeeze on the projected increase in the programme budget. The lack of adjustment for inflation and the merging already constitute significant challenges in arguing the magnitude of the increase. This is without considering any new programme actions.

Figure 1 - Erasmus+ Annual budget evolution

More importantly, the Erasmus+ Annual Budgets will not benefit from the mentioned increase because the current MFF annual allocations were planned to rise more sharply than what is projected in the new MFF, as shown in Figure 1. Furthermore, the proposed MFF indicates a decrease in the relative weight of Erasmus+ within the overall EU budget for the next programme period: increasing the budget by 0,3 points would already result in a significant improvement of the financial projections by around 6 billion EUR and maintain the same proportional share of the EU budget allocated to Erasmus+ in 2028-34.

The ambition of the mobility targets does not match the financial proposal

The EU has set itself a mobility target of 23% of graduates across⁵ the European Education Area by 2030. To achieve the said target, the current allocation to Erasmus+ mobilities in Higher Education should increase by at least 55%⁶ based on the 2025 annual budget⁷. This increase only factors in the budget needed for monthly grants. Other additional support mechanisms, like travel and inclusion measures, would require even further financial contributions. The projected annual budgets in the EU long-term budget, as outlined above, will likely not allow for such an increase.

The vision set by the EU and its Member States to reach the 23% mobility target requires proportionate financial investment. The Erasmus+ programme is undoubtedly the most prominent opportunity for students to engage in international activities. Furthermore, the strategic objectives for the development of 65 European University Alliances involving over 550 institutions to create a transnational educational offer are unlikely to be met within the current long-term budget proposal.

Figure 2: Proposed new actions in the Erasmus+

The pressure on the highly successful Erasmus+ programme is mounting, with other programme sectors gaining momentum under the current and upcoming funding periods, and new actions being added to the programme despite the stable or even limited funding increase outlined in the Commission's proposal. In this context, we are becoming more acutely aware that either the trilogue must result in an eventual higher allocation to Erasmus+, to support its ambitions, or strategic decisions will need to be made to cut funding for some of the proposed existing or new actions. How will the proposal for Talent Scholarships be funded when one single scholarship could consume the budget of up to 23 mobilities? How will the European Solidarity Corps be incorporated into the Erasmus+ budget? Will the School Alliances receive adequate funding when European University Alliances are already struggling with their funding allocations?

With the increased focus on other sectors, as announced by the European Commission, will this result in a drop in funding for higher education overall?

The proposals for the EU's next long-term budget and the regulation establishing the Erasmus+ programme (2028-2034) provide very little clarity on what each sector can anticipate for the programme's future. Promises are made during speeches that budgetary allocation between pillars, different actions and sectors will remain similar. However, the restructuring of the programme and new policy priorities, with a greater emphasis on skills development and talent retention, leave many wondering if that will really be the case. Without a concrete budgetary proposal on the table, each sector is aiming to safeguard its priorities and new activities, fighting for the limited resources available.

These are just some of the many questions that remain unanswered at this stage, and we call on the European Commission to facilitate an open and transparent dialogue with the sector on these issues so that beneficiaries can plan ahead. Equally important, we urge Higher Education Institutions and their stakeholders to raise their concerns regarding the current Erasmus+ 2028-2034 proposal with their national authorities, including Ministries of Finance, as the programme risks becoming systemically underfunded if the current situation holds true - further considering that Member States might actually advocate for a lower overall MFF Budget. Given the security concerns, increasing investment in Erasmus+ would ensure the Union's long-term vision of competitiveness and societal resilience, as highlighted in the Draghi report (2024). One point is utterly clear: investing in Erasmus+ is investing in the prosperous, long-term future of our continent, one that cherishes and protects our common values.

References

- 1 Draghi, M. (2024). The Future of European Competitiveness-In depth analysis and recommendations. European Commission. Retrieved at https://commission.europa.eu/topics/eu-competitiveness/draghi-report_en#paragraph_47059
- 2 Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council establishing the Erasmus+ programme for the period 2028-2034, and repealing Regulations (EU) 2021/817 and (EU) 2021/888. Retrieved at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:52025PC0549>
- 3 Communication from the Commission - A dynamic EU Budget for the priorities of the future - The Multiannual Financial Framework 2028-2034. Retrieved at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52025DC0570&qid=1753978048542>
- 4 European Parliament CULT Committee meeting, 24 September 2025. Retrieved at https://multimedia.europarl.europa.eu/en/webstreaming/cult-committee-meeting_20250924-1430-COMMITTEE-CULT
- 5 Council Recommendation of 13 May 2024 "Europe on the Move" - learning mobility opportunities for everyone (C2024/3364). Retrieved at https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=OJ:C_202403364
- 6 The calculation is made taking into consideration the total number of bachelor's or equivalent level students across the European Education Area, the mobility targets the Member States have adopted, and available information about the potential budget allocation for the next funding period, projecting the same share of the total Erasmus+ budget for higher education mobilities, as well as average duration and grant amount for student mobilities in higher education.
- 7 The 2025 annual work programme for the implementation of Erasmus+: the Union Programme for Education, Training, Youth and Sport. Retrieved at https://erasmus-plus.ec.europa.eu/sites/default/files/2024-10/awp-erasmus-oct-2025_en.PDF

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